

Examining the Elementary School Teachers' Attitude Towards Inclusive Education: A Study of District Anantnag

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ABSTRACT

The current research paper entitled, "Examining The Elementary School Teachers Attitude Towards Inclusive Education: A Study of District Anantnag". The objective of the study was to examine the elementary school teachers attitude towards inclusive education in relation to their gender, institutional type, and teaching experience. The study which was descriptive in nature was conducted on 100 elementary school teachers belonging to different schools of Anantnag. The Teachers were sampled by using simple random sampling technique. For data collection Teachers Attitude Scale towards Inclusive Education (TASTIE-SA) developed by Vishal Sood and Arati Anand was used. The data was analysed by using percentage and t-test. The major findings of the study were;

- *attitude of teachers towards inclusive education is independent of gender.*
- *attitude of teachers towards inclusive education is independent of type of institution they are working.*
- *attitude of teachers towards inclusive education is independent of their Teaching Experience.*

INTRODUCTION

The term “inclusive education” is the combination of two words; “inclusive” and “education”. Inclusive is derived from include. It means, including many things or everything. Inclusive education means “including people of all kind in education, so that they can learn together”.

Inclusive education means that all students in a school, regardless of their strengths or weakness in any area become part of the school community. They are included in the feeling of belonging among other student’s.

Inclusion in education is a process of enabling all children to learn and participate effectively within mainstream school systems. It does not segregate children who have different abilities or needs. Inclusive education is a right-based approach to educating children and includes those who are subject to exclusionary pressures.

In almost every country, some children and adults who cannot compete in school are being excluded from formal education altogether. They are gradually and deliberately pushed out of the school system because schools are not sensitive to their learning styles and backgrounds. In a gesture of sympathy some children are sorted out into categories and placed in separate special schools, away from their peers. This has led to the development of two separate systems of education within countries: regular and special education teaching for students with special needs. However, in recent years the rationale for having two parallel national systems of education has been questioned and the foundation of ‘special education’ has begun to crumble. The thinking that has developed during the last 50 years in the disability field has had significant influences not only on special education but also on practice in regular education. Current thinking and knowledge demand that the responsibility for all learners should remain with the regular classroom teacher.

Why Inclusive Education

There are a number of reasons behind adaptation of inclusion in education:

- Accessible to the disabled in all parts of the country.
- Use of existing infrastructure and resources possible with some modification
- Least cost solution
- The child has the advantage of being in an environment which shares with his/ her peers;
- Congenial company instead of isolation-a natural social environment participation in the general community life.

- Stays with his/her family thus ensuring family funding.

The United Nations and Other International Organizations are encouraging the development of inclusive education systems for several reasons. The most important reason is the human rights for all children to receive education. Providing education for all children in one educational system has educational, social and economic advantages. The UN Salamanca statement 1994 states that:

“Regular schools with this inclusive orientation are the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes, creating welcoming communities, building an inclusive society and achieving education for all; moreover, they provide an effective education to all the majority of children and improve the efficiency and ultimately the cost-effectiveness of the entire education system”.

The UN convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) sets out children's rights in respect of freedom from discrimination and in respect of the representation of their wishes and views.

We are all now familiar with the 1990 world Declaration on Education for All: Meeting basic Learning Needs- The Declaration states that, inter alia:

Basic education should be provided to all children ...To this end, basic education services of quality should be expanded, and consistent measures must be taken to reduce disparities (Article 3.1). (UNESCO, 1998:3).

Persons With Disabilities Act ,1995 (PWD Act) (Equal opportunity, protection of rights and full participation)

The Act stresses the need to provide free of cost education to all children in an appropriate environment till they are 18 years old and further emphasize their rights to measures like:

- Transport facilities to the students with disabilities.
- Architectural Barrier Free Environment.
- The supply of Books, uniforms and Aids and Appliances.
- The Grant of scholarship to students with Disabilities.
- setting up of appropriate forum for the redressal of grievances.
- suitable modification in the examination system.
- Restructuring of curriculum for the benefits of students with hearing impairment.

As mentioned in Section 2.1 of PWD Act (1995), in India disability is measured in five categories- sight, speech, hearing, locomotion, and mental- which excludes disabilities such as Autism. In addition, a person has to be medically certified as having 40% or more of one of these disabilities in order to be counted and so qualified to request ‘benefits ‘.

Simultaneously, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) the Government's millennial Education For All (EFA) umbrella programme for all education schemes, which aims to universalize elementary education, the goals are that all children aged 6-14, including the Enrolment of children with Disabilities.

Fundamental Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education through RTE Act, 2010.

ARTICLE 21A:

The state shall provide Free and Compulsory Education to All children of the age of Six to fourteen (6-14) years in such manner as the state may, by law, Determine.

RTE (Right To Education) Act was passed by parliament in 2009 and made effective from 1st April 2010;

Mandatory provision of the RTE Act: 25% Reservation for disadvantaged children in private schools.

The philosophy of inclusive education thus asserts that education is the right of every child and all children should be given education equally in the same classroom.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Various research studies have been conducted on Inclusive Education by different research scholars across the globe as has been presented chronologically below;

Wahsheh (2024) conducted a study on, "The inclusion of students with disabilities: Teachers attitudes". The objectives of the study were, that the current study examined teachers' attitude with respect to the inclusion of students with disabilities in mainstream classes at Irbid educational governorate. The study employed the descriptive analytical approach using a sample of teachers who were working at QA sabt Irbid (n=487) selected using convenient sampling who completed a (27) items questionnaire assessing the teachers attitudes through three domains (social, psychological, academic). The results obtained showed that the main score of teachers attitudes with respect to the inclusion of students with disabilities in mainstream classes was (2.19) with negative attitudes. Statistically significant differences were found with respect to teaching experience, in favor of less than 10 years, while no significant differences were found with respect to gender. The study recommended to provide further guidance and training services for teachers to raise their awareness level with respect to the importance of the inclusion of students with disabilities in mainstream classes.

Mares (2024) conducted a study on, "Social Inclusion Attitude, an Insight among Teachers: Disadvantaged Areas". The objectives of the study were the concept of social Inclusion is about accepting diversity and acknowledging the need to find solutions and mechanisms to meet the specific particularities of all types of people. The issue of social inclusion was particularly relevant in the past century context, and it has maintained

its topicality in the socio-economic and political context of the 21st century. The present research is a analysis of the attitude of a group of secondary school teachers on next research topics; self-evaluation of knowledge about social inclusion; self-perception regarding its importance and its impact on the school and local community; their perception of social inclusion; their opinions about the causes of social exclusion and the identification of effective strategies and best practices in facilitating social inclusion. The aim of our approach has been to identify the perspective of the teachers working in high schools from disadvantaged areas, especially in the rural ones, in order to identify some supporting models and to find future paths of specific intervention. We believe that our approach can lead to the identification of effective tools for the cooperation and collaboration between the pre-university and university levels for planning activities related to teacher training on inclusive education and equal opportunities, and for being able to facilitate the access of disadvantaged students to all kinds of education.

Bethere (2023) conducted a study on, "Teachers Attitudes towards Inclusive Education Latvian and Lithuanian Experiences". The objectives of the study were, that the inclusive education is a continuous process of transformation of the education system. It is both an approach to teaching and learning, as well as a different organization of the educational process that welcomes all students regardless of their social skills and physical and intellectual abilities. The qualitative implementation of inclusive education requires competent staff. The study reflects a comparative study carried out in Latvia and Lithuania, and it focuses on Latvian and Lithuanian teachers' attitude self-assessment regarding the implementation of inclusive education a three-dimensional model, including the cognitive, affective, and behavior components, are used for the study. The technical Manual for Attitudes towards Teaching All Students Instrument developed by Gregory Jess L, .and Noto Lori A, has been applied in the study. The SPSS 25.0 programme, Pearson correlation, and one-way ANOVA tests were used for the statistical analysis of the data. The results reveal, and generally confirm, differences in the structure of Latvian and Lithuanian teachers' attitudes, as well as emphasize the importance of teachers and supports specialists' competence improvement to ensure optimal teaching and learning processes for all learners involved in the educational process.

Jurca (2023) conducted a study on, "Exploring Attitudinal Dimensions of Inclusive Education; Predictive Factors among Romanian Teachers ". The objectives of the study were, that the inclusive attitudes are considered an important predictor of the quality of educational inclusion. Child-related, teacher related and environment-related factors were measured over time in connection with teachers' positive attitudes. This study aimed to contribute with insights from Romania to the comprehensive understanding of the attitudinal dimensions of inclusive education and the factors that predict it. A quantitative, non-experimental, correlational research design was undertaken in September-October 2022 to determine the factors that can significantly predict the dimensions of

inclusive attitudes. A convenience sample of 1040 Romanian teachers participated in the study. The MATIES scale was used to measure the dimensions of inclusive attitudes; cognitive, affective, and behavioral. The results showed that there are a number of universally known factors that have been found to predict inclusive attitudes, like the school environment, close relationships with people with disabilities, and training in special education. Their predictive power is relatively low, ranging between 2% and 9%, suggesting the presence of unexplored influential variables and emphasizing the need for future studies to consider additional factors. The specific and significant factors for Romanian culture was found to be the need for training in special education. The data can be informative for curriculum designers, training providers, and policy makers, signaling the need for comprehensive training in special education in the initial and continuous training of all teachers.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Today, inclusive education is a widely accepted approach of the 21st century because it helps in unfolding the hidden potential of the students, ensure the right of every individual without any discrimination and make a universally inclusive environment for the maximum development of the children. Inclusive education facilitates the idea of acceptance; promotes wider social acceptance peace, and cooperation. The most important responsibility of the proper function of inclusive education depends upon the involvement and cooperation of teachers, parents, and community leaders. To the successful implementation of inclusive education, a positive attitude is required. It may be of society, peers, parents of the children, teachers, administrators etc. The most important for the successful implementation of an inclusive approach in the classroom depends upon the attitude of teachers. Therefore, prioritizing inclusive education as an integral part of the education system is not enough but the attitude of teachers for inclusion is equally important. Teacher's attitude is important for the successful implementation of inclusive education and contributing great impact on the teaching-learning process in the classroom (Sharma et al,2008; Hattie, 2009). Castell and Bayle (2013) and Goddard and Evans (2018) reported that primary pre-service teachers 'attitude towards inclusion were generally positive and strengthened across the training. The negative attitude of teachers towards Inclusive Education affects teaching effectiveness and teaching learning process of students negatively and creates a hurdle for the success of inclusive education (Gol,,Schreur and Yeger,2010; Cassady 2011; Taylor and Ringaben, 2012),Finally, conclude that attitude, concerns, and perception of teachers towards inclusive education affect the implementation of it.Since,the teachers attitude has a significant contribution to successful implementation of inclusive education, particularly in India, therefore, it is needed to be investigated in the delimited area.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The research title for the purposed study was:

“Examining the Elementary School Teachers Attitudes Inclusive Education in Relation to their Gender, Institutional Type, and Teaching Experience: A Study of District Anantnag”.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study was conducted to achieve the following objectives:

1. To study the level of attitude of teachers towards inclusive education.
2. To study the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education with respect to their, gender, institutional type, and teaching experience.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Ho1: There would be no significant difference between teachers regarding their attitude towards inclusive education on the basis of gender.

Ho2: There would be no significant difference between teachers regarding their attitude towards inclusive education on the basis of institutional type.

Ho3: There would be no significant difference between teachers regarding their attitude towards inclusive education on the basis of teaching experience.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Attitude of Teachers towards Inclusive Education: Inclusive Education refers to an education system. Which accommodates all children regardless of their physical, intellectual, social, emotional, or other conditions. For the proposed study, Attitude of Teachers towards Inclusive Education refers to the scores obtained by using Attitude of Teachers towards Inclusive Education by *Sood and Anand (2011)*.

Elementary School Teachers: Elementary school teachers who impart education to classes 1st to 8th in District Anantnag (India). The children in these classes are generally aged between 6 and 14 years.

DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The following were the delimitation's of the proposed study:

1. The study was restricted to the Elementary school teachers of Anantnag District (J and K)UT only.
2. The present study was restricted to the few demographic variables i.e., Gender, Institutional Type, and Teaching experience.
3. The study was also be restricted to the sample of 100 elementary school teachers.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

The detailed description of the procedure and plan used by the researcher has been mentioned in this section.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

The present study was a survey kind of description study where the researcher attempted to find out the Elementary School Teachers Attitude towards Inclusive Education on the basis of Gender, Institutional Type, and Teaching Experience: A study of District Anantnag.

A Descriptive research design was used for the study as this method is concerned with surveying, describing, and investigating the existing phenomenon or issues, conditions, and relationships that exist.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of the study constituted all the Govt and Private school teachers working at elementary level of Anantnag District (J and K) UT. However, the sample was taken from the below mentioned schools by chit-fold method –enrolled during the session 2023-24.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The sample of the study consisted of 100 Govt and Private school teachers were selected across the Gender, Institutional Type, and Teaching Experience. However, the random sampling technique was used for the present study, (chit-fold method). This method involved assigning numbers to all the teachers in the population and randomly drawing numbers to select the sample. The chit-fold method was chosen for its ability to provide each teacher with an equal chance of selection, thereby minimizing selection bias and enhancing the generalizability to the findings. The brief description of Sample has been shown in the following table:

Table 1. shows the description of Sample Gender Wise

S.No	Name of Schools	Sample	Gender	
			Male	Female
01	Govt Middle School, Krangsoo, Anantnag	20	05	15
02	Govt Middle School, Pehroo, Anantnag	20	05	15
03	Govt Middle School, Krangsoo, Anantnag	15	05	10
04	Iqra Public School, Krangsoo, Anantnag	15	10	05
05	Paradise Valley School, Pehroo, Anantnag	15	05	10
06	Delight Presentation School, Krangsoo, Anantnag	15	10	05
Total =100			Total = 40 Teachers	Total = 60 Teachers

Table 2 shows the description of Sample Institutional Type wise

S.No	Name of the School	Sample	Institutional Type	
			Govt	Private
01	Govt Middle School, Krangsoo, Ang.	20	15	05
02	Govt Middle School, Pehroo, Anantnag	20	10	10
03	Govt Middle School, Shamsipora Ang.	15	05	10
04	Iqra Public School, Krangsoo, Anantnag	15	05	10
05	Paradise Valley School, Pehroo, Ang.	15	10	05
06	Delight Presentation School, Krangsoo, Ang.	15	10	05
Total = 100			Total = 55	Total = 45

Table 3 shows the description of sample Teaching Experience wise

S.NO	Name of The School	Sample	Teaching Experience	
			More Than 10 Years	Less Than 10 Years
01	Govt Middle School,Krangsoo, Ang.	20	15	05
02	Govt Middle School,Pehroo Ang.	20	15	05
03	Govt Middle School,Shamsipora,Ang	15	05	10
04	Iqra Public School,Krangsoo,Ang	15	10	05
05	Paradise Valley School,Pehroo,Ang	15	10	05
06	Delight Presentation School, Krangsoo	15	10	05

TOOLS FOR THE PRESENT STUDY

For data collection Teachers Attitude Scale Towards Inclusive Education (TASTIE-SA) developed by Vishal Sood and Arati Anand was used.

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION

The required data for the present study were collected by the researcher personally from the

selected elementary schools of Anantnag. After taking the permission from the principles of the selected elementary schools, the data was collected by using Teachers Attitude Scale towards Inclusive Education (TASTIE-SA) test developed by Vishal Sood and Arati Anand. The researcher collected the data during the month of Sep and Oct 2024 on different days. During collection of the data researcher met with teachers of the respective schools and introduced himself/herself to the teachers and told the teachers about the purpose of study. Researcher explained basic information regarding the tool to the teachers and were promised that the collected information will be kept confidential and will be used for research purpose only.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected was analyzed by using percentage and t-test.

DATA INTERPRETATION AND FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

FIRST OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The first objective of the study was, “To study the level of Attitude of Teachers Towards Inclusive Education”. The data related to the objective were collected and was analyzed with the help of percentage as shown in table 4.1 below;

Table 4 Shows the Level of Attitude of Teachers towards Inclusive Education

S.NO	Range of Raw scores	Range of Z-scores	Level of Attitude	Number of Teachers Falling in the Range	Percentage
01	127 & Above	+2.01 and Above	Extremely Favourable	06 Teachers	6%
02	116-126	+1.26 to + 2.00	Most Favourable	19 Teachers	19%
03	105-115	+0.51 to +1.25	Above Average Favourable	18 Teachers	18%
04	90-104	-0.50 to +0.50	Moderate Attitude	15 Teachers	15%

05	80-89	-0.50 to -1.25	Below Average Unfavourable	02 Teachers	02%
06	69-79	-1.25 to -2.00	Most Unfavourable	00 Teachers	00%
07	68-& Below	-2.01 to below	Extremely Unfavourable	00 Teachers	00%

From table 4, it is quite clear that 6% of school teachers of district Anantnag are as such which have extremely favourable attitude towards inclusive education, whereas 19%, 18%, 15% and 2% of school teachers of district Anantnag are as such which have Most Favourable, Above Average Favourable, Moderate and Below Average unfavorable respectively attitude towards inclusive education.

SECOND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The second objective of the study was, “To study the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education based on gender”. The data related to the objective was collected and analysed by using t-test as has been discussed below;

Table 5 Shows different values of independent sample t-test between Male and Female teachers towards inclusive education

Gender	N	t-value	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Level of Significance
Male	40	.016	98	.987	Not significant at 0.05 level
Female	60				

From above table 5, it is pretty evident that the t-value is .016 with df= 98 whose two tailed significance value is .987 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence the value is insignificant at 0.05 LOS. In view of this, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education based upon their gender” is accepted.

Thus, it can be concluded that the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education is

independent of gender.

SECOND PART OF THE SECOND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The second part of the second objective of the study was, “To study the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education based on institutional type”. The data related to the objective was collected and analyzed by using t-test as has been discussed below;

Table 6 Shows different values of independent sample t-test between Private and Govt.

School teachers towards inclusive education

Institutional Type	N	t-value	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Level of Significance
Private	45	.836	98	.405	Not significant at 0.05 level
Govt	55				

From above table 6, it is pretty evident that the t-value is .836 with df= 98 whose two tailed significance value is .405 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence the value is insignificant at 0.05 LOS. In view of this, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education based upon their institutional type” is accepted.

Thus, it can be concluded that the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education is independent of type of institution they are working.

THIRD PART OF THE SECOND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The Third part of the second objective of the study was, “To study the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education based on their Teaching Experience”. The data related to the objective was collected and analyzed by using t-test as has been discussed below;

Table 7 Shows different values of independent sample t-test between More Experienced and Less Experienced teachers towards inclusive education

Experience	N	t- value	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Level of Significance
Experienced Teachers (Teaching Experience of More than 10 Years)	65	1.021	98	.310	Not significant at 0.05 level
Less Experienced Teachers (Teaching Experience of Less than 10Years)	35				

From above table 7, it is pretty evident that the t-value is 1.021 with $df=98$ whose two tailed significance value is .310 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence the value is insignificant at 0.05 LOS. In view of this, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education based upon their Teaching Experience” is accepted.

Thus, it can be concluded that the attitude of teachers towards inclusive education is independent of their Teaching Experience.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Suggestions for Further Research on Attitudes of Elementary School Teachers towards Inclusive Education in Respect to their Gender, Institutional Type and Teaching Experience in District Anantnag.

Comparative Analysis: Comparative study of Govt and Private school teachers for difference in attitude towards Inclusive Education based on Institutional Type.

Gender Perspectives: Differences in attitudes towards inclusive education among male and female teachers. Reflect on societal expectations and past encounters that could shape these sentiments.

Effectiveness of Professional Development: Explore the effects, on teacher attitudes toward inclusive education based on gender and years of teaching experience in a professional development program.

Longitudinal Study: Implement a longitudinal study to track changes in attitudes overtime as teachers gain more experience or engage in additional training on inclusive practices.

Student Outcomes: Research the correlation between teachers attitudes toward inclusive education and student outcomes, particularly for students with special needs.

Qualitative insights: Use interviews or focus groups together in-depth Qualitative data on teachers' beliefs and experiences regarding inclusive education paying attention to gender and teaching experience.

Classroom Practices: Analyze the relationship between teachers' attitude and their actual classroom practices regarding inclusion, considering how gender and teaching experience might shape their teaching strategies.

These suggestions can help to create a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing teachers attitudes towards inclusive education in the context of District Anantnag.

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